

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

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ABSTRACT: Time is a vital resource available to all human beings. The current research, therefore, aims to clarify the relationship between time management and the quality of production, the disclosure of how the engineer organizes his/her time, and the extent to which cultural and societal factors influence the use of time. This study aims to explore the effects of working place on employee productivity with a quantitative approach, the data was collected using a survey method. The survey was adopted from previous literature and data was analysed using SPSS. The study sample included several engineers from different fields in different companies. The research has produced several findings, including the importance of time planning, which is an essential factor contributing to increasing production rates, and the different perspectives of engineers to define and understand the term time management, which leads to the finding that the time factor is a significant factor for all engineers to get successful results at the end of the day. Finally, the analyses and the final results were discussed to clarify the importance of the time management element and its relationship to the workplace and to reach conclusions and nominations.

KEYWORDS: Efficiency, Performance, Planning, Time management, Work Productivity, Working from Home, Working from Office.

INTRODUCTION

Organizations have increasingly realized the importance of time management during the last 20 years. Because of rising worldwide competitiveness and demand for fast provision of products and services, work time has become more crucial. Over the last two years, the world has been destroyed by a pandemic that has afflicted all populations and countries. Companies have been directed to direct their staff to work from home in order to overcome the epidemic and ensure that it continues to work.

Time is a valuable resource in everyone's life. It is accessible to all humans. It is distinguished by several characteristics. It is a matter of expiration, and what happens is irreversible, making it a psychological resource that impacts the lives of individuals and communities of various characteristics and nature. They have the same amount of time, but they differ in how they use it and how well they arrange it. There is no agreement on the definition of time management in past studies. Although many authors referred to Lakein (1973)'s definition, which suggested that time management involves determining needs, setting goals to achieve these needs, and prioritizing and planning tasks required to achieve these goals, several other definitions were proposed. Thus, time management has been referred to as: a technique for managing time (Jex and Elacqua, 1999; Davis, 2000; Macan, 1994, 1996; Macan et al., 1990; Mudrack, 1997); a technique for adequate time use, especially having enough time to accomplish the tasks required (Orpen, 1994; Slaven and Totterdell, 1993; Woolfolk and Woolfolk, 1986); Planning and allocating time (Burt and Kemp, 1994; Francis-Smythe and Robertson, 1999a); the degree to which individuals perceive their use of time to be structured and purposive (Bond and Feather, 1988; Strongman and Burt, 2000; Sabelis, 2001; Vodanovich and Seib, 1997).

Other researchers identified time management as a way of getting insight into time use (Koolhaas et al., 1992); a technique to increase the time available to pursue activities (King et al., 1986); practices intended to maximize intellectual productivity (Britton and Tesser, 1991); an application of self-regulation processes in the temporal domain (Griffiths, 2003); coping behavior in at-risk populations (King et al., 1986); self-regulation strategies aimed at discussing plans, and their efficiency (Eilam and Aharon, 2003). Moreover, the use of procedures that are designed to help the individual to achieve his or her desired goals (Hall and Hirsch, 1982); ways to assess the relative importance of activities through the development of a prioritization plan (Kaufman-Scarborough and Lindquist, 1999); clusters of behavior that are deemed to facilitate productivity and alleviate

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

stress (Lay and Schouwenburg,1993).

Time is an essential resource in human life and time derives its importance in the lives of individuals and organizations as an essential element for regulating the way of life and achieving goals. However, its use varies according to different cultures, surroundings, and different objectives to complete. Work pressures and poor management of time are factors that negatively affect outcomes and quality of production. There is a need to assess the difference between managing time through working from home or working from the office and which way can have a greater influence on work productivity.

The research objectives rely on clarifying the importance of the time management factor for engineers who work from home or the office. Identifying and clarifying the relationship between time management methods and their impact on work outputs. Clarification of the relationship between the workplace and its impact on time management in completing office tasks. And finally, finding results showing the best place to work and achieving satisfactory efficiency in job quality and productivity. Effective time management for engineers will help leaders, entrepreneurs, and small business owners achieve their goals. Managing time wisely improves work-life balance and increases happiness. Good time management also reduces stress and allows engineers to achieve their goals faster and easier. Access to reliable results to recognize the importance of the workplace.

Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

The increasing salience of time is reflected in theoretical as well as practical publications. A number of authors discussed the need for better incorporating time in theoretical models and research designs (e.g., Ancona et al., 2001; George and Jones, 2000; Wright, 2002). Others focused on the ways in which people in organizations manage their time, and on ways in which these efforts can be improved (e.g. Macan,1994).

Time Management Theory

There is a lack of both a definition and a theory of time management. The topic of "how and why does time management work?" remains unresolved. Only Macan (1994) established a time management model for time management tasks that includes antecedent, mediating, and result variables. According to Macan (1994), time management training programmes promote three types of time management behaviors: setting goals and priorities, time management mechanics, and organizational preference. Macan believes that these activities result in perceptual control of time or a sense of time control. Furthermore, it is hypothesized that time management behavior and job induced and physical stress, job happiness, and job performance all mediate perceptual control of time. According to the findings, time management training is only proportionate to the amount of time management behavior, goal setting, and priorities. He claimed that setting goals and priorities and time management mechanisms have a positive relationship with perceptual control over time, while preferences for organizations do not. Job-induced and somatic stress are negatively correlated, and job satisfaction is positively correlated with time management behavior and is regulated by perceptual control of time. Perceptual control of time is not significantly related to work performance. These results mean that by implementing time management technology, people are able to control what can be done during the working day. This feeling in turn has a positive impact on job satisfaction and job-induced and physical stress.

Three replication studies (Adams and Jex, 1999; Davis, 2000; Jex and Elacqua, 1999) provided only partial support to Macan's (1994) model. Firstly, Jex and Elacqua (1999) found that perceived control of time partially mediated the relations between goal setting and prioritizing, and preference for organization on the one hand, and strain on the other hand. Secondly, Adams and Jex (1999) found that perceived control of time mediated between setting goals and priorities, mechanics of time management, and preference for organization on the one hand, and health and job satisfaction on the other hand. Setting goals and priorities and preference for organization were positively related to perceived control, whereas mechanics of time management were negatively related to perceived control of time.

Finally, Davis (2000) found that perceived control of time only acted as a mediator in the relationship between preference for organization and the outcome variables of job-related tension, somatic tension, and job satisfaction. Claessens et al. (2004) used a different time management scale to test the mediation model over time. A planning scale was used instead. This study also revealed partial mediation of control of time.

In conclusion, these studies found some support for Macan's (1994) process model that hypothesized perceived control of time to fully mediate between time management behaviors and job- and person-related outcomes. As for the relationship between particular time management behaviors and outcomes, it was found that planning showed the most significant results.

Effects of Time Management Behavior on Accomplishing the tasks

Time management activity has been studied in relation to several other outcome variables. The first group of studies looked into effects on proximal variables, such as accurately estimated time duration (Burt and Kemp, 1994; Francis-Smythe and Robertson, 1999a); spending time on high-priority tasks (Hall and Hirsch, 1982); the ability to readjust plans to improve progress rate (Eilam and Aharon, 2003). Other studies have examined effects on performance in work and academic settings, such

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

as sales performance (Barling et al., 1996); job performance (Davis, 2000; Macan, 1994); college grades (Britton and Tesser, 1991; Trueman and Hartley, 1996); academic performance (Burt and Kemp, 1994); grade point average (Britton and Tesser, 1991); and total study habits score (Bond and Feather, 1988). The third group of studies has investigated the effects of attitudinal and stress-related outcomes, such as perceived control of time (Adams and Jex, 1999; Davis, 2000; Jex and Elacqua, 1999; Francis-Smythe and Robertson, 1999a; Macan, 1994); job satisfaction (Davis, 2000; Macan, 1994); role overload (Burt and Kemp, 1994); job-related and somatic tension (Davis, 2000; Macan, 1994); work-family interference (Adams and Jex, 1999); strain (Jex and Elacqua, 1999; Lang, 1992); emotional exhaustion (Peeters and Rutte, 2005); and health (Bond and Feather, 1988).

The proximal outcomes of time estimation and spending time on high-priority tasks were positively affected. Francis-Smythe and Robertson (1999a) concluded that participants who perceived themselves as practicing time management behaviors estimated the expected time durations more accurately than those who did not but tended to underestimate time in passing. The authors emphasized the role of motivation, as they found that more motivated respondents had better results in planning. There appeared to be a difference between the academic and job-related performance outcomes. College grades and total study habits score were positively affected, but the expected relation between time management behaviors and job performance was modest or even non-significant. Macan (1994) failed to find a positive relationship with job performance, whereas Barling et al. (1996) did find a relation with sales performance, but only for those participants scoring high on achievement motivation.

Results on stress-related outcomes showed that time management was positively related to perceived control of time, job satisfaction, and health, and negatively to job-induced and somatic tension, strain, and psychological distress. Jex and Elacqua (1999) found a moderating effect of time management behavior on the relation between work-family conflict and strain, with a stronger relation between work-family conflict and health for participants who applied time management techniques. This moderation is similar to what Peeters and Rutte (2005) found, time management moderated the relation between high demands and low autonomy on the one hand, and emotional exhaustion on the other. In conclusion, research has found positive effects of time management behavior on proximal outcomes, performance, and stress-related outcomes. However, the results obtained for performance appear to be the weakest within these three categories.

Working from Home vs Working from Office

Investigations of the impact of remote work as a flexible form of work performance began as early as the 1970s. The term “telecommuting” was first coined by Jack Nilles (1975) in the 1970s when he was working remotely as an engineer on NASA's communications systems and referred to his work as telecommuting. He later defined telecommuting as working outside of a standard workplace through telecommunications and computer-based technology (Nilles, 1994). Belanger and Collins (1998), who coined the term distributed work, also researched flexible workplace and environmental issues. According to their definition, distributed work is an agreement that allows employees to share work-related tasks away from the central location of the business or its physical organizational location. The most well-known type of distributed work is telecommuting. In addition, this type of work arrangement is recognized as ‘telework’ or ‘remote work’ (Gajendran and Harrison, 2007).

Based on recent studies (Irawanto, Novianti and Roz, 2021), the higher the intensity of remote work, the more satisfied employees are. In the group of people who spend only ¼ of their time working remotely, 82% of the respondents said they want to work remotely more often (Buffer and AngelList, 2020). A joint study by Owl Labs and Global Workplace Analytics found that 71% of people working remotely are happy with their job, while 55% of people working in the office are satisfied with their job. Remote workers say they're comfortable in their jobs 29% more than on-site workers (Owl Labs, Global Workplace Analytics, 2019). The impact of telecommuting on labor capacity is still a controversial issue (Schall, 2019, Nuwer, 2016). The development of remote employment generates several polemical judgments. Highly skilled workers face a choice: reap the benefits of interactions in the office but bear the cost of commuting to work; or save on transportation but not receive the benefit of the effects of agglomeration and incur additional housing costs since part of the living space must be used as an office (Wang et al., 2021). Businesses are faced with a choice between reduced productivity due to reduced agglomeration effects and reduced office costs.

According to recent scientific research, the proportion of distance employment that maximizes labor productivity with a remote job was determined to be within 20% to 40%, equivalent to 1-2 working days in a 5-day working week (Gajendran and Harrison, 2007). Until the inflection point is discovered, though, teleworking increases the productivity of both skilled and unskilled workers without significantly altering the balance of demand for office and residential premises and at the same time increasing the potential for using information and telecommunication technologies (Nuwer, 2016). Following the COVID-19 pandemic, companies and organizations now aim to engage the work, workforce, and workplace in a new system that identifies the work as a set of tasks to be completed, rather than linking it with a specific location. Working from home is a term that refers to work done at home, regardless of whether the individual performing the work is an employee of an organization or is self-employed. Telecommuting is used to describe when an employee uses stationary or portable devices to do their office work outside the office. This allows the flexibility of using telecommunications to connect with colleagues in real time.

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

Other benefits include autonomy, absence of distractions, decreased travel, and increased productivity, which is the main variables motivating people to work at home (Lakshmi et al., 2017; Meenakshi, V, and Ravichandran, 2013). Basically, employee work productivity is the result of a series of behaviors that are carried out by employees in work situations (Hartini, Fakhrorazi, and Islam, 2019) and determine the viability and profitability of the organization (Islam, Osman, Othman, and Raihan, 2019; Van Nguyen, Doan, Nu, Quoc, and Quynh, 2021).

Productivity is also an important mechanism for management to clarify performance goals and standards and to motivate individuals to ensure the sustainability of the organization (Shaki and Khoshsaligheh, 2017). It is also a rating system used in most companies to evaluate an employee's abilities (Khuong and Quoc, 2016). The WFH (work from home) situation is likely to become part of future office work and as such, it is important to understand the effects of the three aspects of future work -the worker, workspace, and work- relative to the WFH experience.

Worker Characteristics

The WFH experience is inevitably influenced by worker demographics, including gender, age, and income. Even in 2021, gender gaps in the workplace and at home persist, which might lead to the assumption that women have lower productivity than men because women spend more time on household chores and child caregiving. In addition to the demographic factors, WFH may create different challenges for workers with different occupational backgrounds. Prior studies have investigated the impact of WFH on productivity within specific groups of workers (e.g., workers of a Chinese travel agency, and workers of the U.S. Patent and Trademark Office). However, there has not been a study that investigated the effects of WFH on productivity across different occupational groups. A transition to remote work would likely have a low risk of loss in efficiency for workers who primarily engage directly with computer workstations throughout their day (e.g., programmers) as opposed to individuals working in jobs that require mixed tasks in an interpersonal environment (e.g., health care office workers).

Importantly, worker health has been consistently associated with productivity, such that the more health issues workers report the worse their productivity levels are. Although it may be more easily concluded that these relationships would exist similarly in remote contexts, there are limited studies that examine the impact of worker health on productivity while WFH.

Workspace Context

Workspace context plays a major role in shaping the work experience. Satisfaction with one's workspace, privacy, and the ability to personalize the workspace are predictors of workers' productivity. The shift from working in a well-established office space to working from home can be challenging for many office workers. Such challenges can be stressful and might negatively affect a worker's desire to work and thus reduce their productivity. Having the optimal physical setup, proper ergonomics, and the necessary equipment is crucial to creating an effective workspace that boosts productivity and increases the workers' engagement with their workstations. In their analysis of the workforce shift to the WFH, Moretti et al. explained that workers are expected to engage extensively with their workstations while working from home, and therefore presented their suggestions for a comfortable workstation (i.e., an adjustable desk and chair to prevent back and joints pain, along with a footrest, and an adjustable monitor screen).

Research also shows that separating the workspaces from living spaces is an important factor when working remotely. It is recommended to have a dedicated workspace to create

Physical boundaries, help workers establish a productive work atmosphere, increase workers' desire to stay longer hours at their workstation and signal to other household members that they do not want to be distracted.

Work Context

Another important consideration in worker productivity and work experience when WFH is the ability of workers to set and maintain appropriate boundaries between work duties and house responsibilities. With role conflicts, workers used to find it challenging to manage work and family/life commitments, even before the pandemic era. With workers shifting to WFH abruptly with the pandemic, new forms of conflicts between work and life occurred. When working and living in the same space, setting boundaries between work and life becomes more challenging. For example, the sense of time might fade in the homogeneous work-home environment, and workers might elongate their working hours, start working earlier, later, or on the weekends. Some workers might embrace the flexibility in their work hours while other workers might have no choice but to schedule their working hours around their household members or responsibilities. At the same time, the unclear boundaries between home and office might have increased work expectations. For example, Peasley et al. found that sales personnel felt burned out when trying to meet the management's expectations and they believed that job expectations became higher as soon as they started working from home during the COVID-19 pandemic. With this increase in expectations, workers might be tasked with more duties and expected to deliver additional work, increasing working hours and requiring them to spend additional time at their workstations.

Work stress experienced by employees, if not managed properly, will result in low work productivity and lead to an increase in absence (Ahmed and Ramzan, 2013; Kakkos and Trivellas, 2011; Yahaya, Yahaya, Bon, Ismail, and Ing, 2011). Also,

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

from previous studies and analysis and criticism of the tools used in knowledge of the importance of time management and its effective role through working from home in achieving high productivity and quality formulated the following hypotheses of scientific research within the framework of our study follows:

H1: Working from home is more effective in time management than working from the office
H2: Working from home increase work quality and productivity

H3: Time attitude behavior improvement has a good effect on time management skills (TimePlanning)

H4: Time waster behaviors have a bad effect on improving time management skills (TimePlanning)

H5: Good time management behavior skills (time planning) increase work quality and productivity

Figure 1. The Proposed Research Model

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Since the objective of this research is to Improve and clarify the effect of time management on employee productivity and job performance, and also which the best workplace can improve time management and work quality. To clarify the impact of the workplace relationship on time management and the efficiency of employees. The quantitative research method has been used through with the model of analytic correlation design and cross-sectional approach. An online questionnaire sent to a number of engineers (127) whose nature and workplace are different.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The research instrument is an online modified questionnaire adapted from the time management questionnaire (TMQ, Britton and Tesser, 1991) for time planning and time attitude. Assessing job performance using brief self-report scales, Madero, G. S., Ortiz, M. O.E., Ramírez, J., and Olivas Luján, M. R. (2020),- For the workplace efficiency questions (Bao et al., 2020; Madero et al., 2020) , Work productivity (Ramos-Villagrana, Barrada, Fernandez-del-Rio, and Koopmans, 2019) . The questionnaire consists of (Respondents information's- Time Management behavior (short and long planning)-Time attitude-workplace efficiency- Time Wasters-Work productivity). The data that was collected with the questionnaire was transferred into SPSS 26. The questionnaire was carried out remotely via emails using GoogleForms (2021). The questionnaire survey consisted of 6 sections. The first section contained: 1) general information about the respondents (gender, age of the respondent, Marital status, Working place and Total amount income monthly). The second section was developed to learn the respondents' behavior towards time management (Time Planning). The third section was developed to learn the respondents' attitudes towards time planning management (Time Attitude). The fourth section was developed to learn the respondents' attitudes towards remote work, studying the preferred form of work, its

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

advantages and disadvantages, and assessing its effectiveness and the factors that affect it (Workplace Efficiency). The fifth section was developed to learn *from the respondents' attitudes toward* time wasters (Time Waster). The sixth section was developed to learn the respondents' attitudes towards work productivity (Work Productivity) These questions were assessed using a 5-point Likert Scale (Always, Frequently, Sometimes, Infrequently and Never) The primary indicator for assessing labor efficiency is the indicator of productivity (Langemeier, 2018).

RESEARCH RESULTS

Reliability and Validity

To measure the Reliability and Validity of the study tool (questionnaire) (Cronbach's Alpha equation) to ascertain the consistency of the study tool on the sample of research, the table 1 shows the constant factors of the study tool .**Table 1** shows that the reliability the variables is between a minimum of 0.549 to a maximum of 0.872. This indicates that the questionnaire has a high degree of consistency that can be relied upon according to the Nunnally scale and is adopted at a minimum of 0.70 (Jum Nunnally and Ira Bernstein 199, pp264-265)

Table 1. Reliability Analysis

Reliability Statistics(variables)		
Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Time Planning	0.872	17
Time Attitude	0.549	4
Workplace Efficiency	0.782	4
Time Waster	0.642	4
Work Productivity	0.787	12

Demographic of the Sample

Table 2 shows demographic data of the questionnaire in which males have the 59.1% from the sample and females have 40.9% from the sample. Most of the respondents were singles with income ranging from 0 to 10000. About the working place we find 72.4% work from the office and 27.6% work from home.

Table 2 Sample of the study

Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percent %
Gender	Male	75
	Female	52
	Total	127
Age	20~29	75
	30~39	38
	40~49	11
	50 +	3
	Total	127
Marital status	Single	68
	Married	22
	Total	127
Working Place	Working from home	35
	Working from the office	92
	Total	127
Total monthly income	0-10,000 EGP	75
	10,000-20,000 EGP	37
	20,000-30,000 EGP	6
	30,000 +	9
	Total	127

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

Correlation Table Between Study Variables

Table 3 shows that all correlation factors between the independent variables (time attitude-time waster) and the dependent variable (time management) were statistically significant at a spiritual level of 0.01 and 0.05. The values of the correlation factors ranged between (0.526**) and (0.432**) and indicated a strong correlation between each independent variable and the dependent variable. As for the workplace variable and its relationship to time management, the function was not statistical significance at a moral level of 0.01 and 0.05, where its correlation factor (-0.93), indicating that there was no correlation between the workplace and time management.

Table 3. Correlation

		Time Attitude	Workplace Efficiency	Time Waster	Time Management (Time Planning)
Time Attitude	Pearson Correlation	1	-0.271-**	0.376**	0.526**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.002	0.000	0.000
	N	127	127	127	127
Workplace Efficiency	Pearson Correlation	-0.271-**	1	-0.150-	-0.93-
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.002		0.93	0.298
	N	127	127	127	127
Time Waster	Pearson Correlation	0.376**	-0.150-	1	0.432**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.93		0.000
	N	127	127	127	127
Time Management (Time Planning)	Pearson Correlation	0.526**	-0.93-	0.432**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.298	0.000	
	N	127	127	127	127

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES TESTING

From the results of hypothesis testing (see Table 4), it was found for H1 that working from home has no significant effect on work productivity and quality because it has a Correlation Coefficient Value ≤ 0 according to (Table 4) This contradicts the theory and previous research that claims that working from home increases employee productivity (Baker et al., 2007; Lim and Teo, 2000), Also the result of (H2) show that working from home has no significant effect on work quality and productivity because it has a Correlation Coefficient Value ≤ 0 according to (Table 4.5.4), Likewise, (H3) is accepted because it has a Correlation Coefficient Value ≥ 0 according to (Table 4.5.4), which show that time attitude behavior improvement has a significant effect on time management skills (Time Planning), (H4) is accepted because it has a Correlation Coefficient Value ≥ 0 according to (Table 4), which show that time waster behaviors have a bad effect on improving time management skills (Time Planning), (H5) is accepted because it has a Correlation Coefficient Value ≥ 0 according to (Table 4), which show that Good time management behavior skills (time planning) have a significant effect on increase work quality and productivity experienced by employees From the results of previous research, when employees have good time management skills and can divide their time effectively between preparing for work and accomplishing tasks, they can get very productive and high-quality outputs. This, in turn, has a positive impact on work productivity (Baker et al., 2007; Darcy et al., 2012; Darko-Asumadu et al., 2018; Dhas, 2015).

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

Table 4. Hypotheses Testing

Research Hypotheses	Correlation Coefficient Value	Significance	Conclusion	Approved /Rejected
1-Working from home is more effectively in time management than working from office (H1)	-0.93-	Not significant	There is no sufficient evidence that working from home has a positive effect on time management behavior than working from the office.	Rejected
2- Working from home increase work quality and productivity (H2)	-0.127-	Not significant	There is no sufficient evidence that working from home has a positive effect on work productivity and quality.	Rejected
3- Time attitude behavior improvement has a good effect on time management skills (Time Planning) (H3)	0.526**	Significant	There is sufficient evidence that time attitude behavior improvement has a good effect on time management skills (Time Planning)	Approved
4-Time waster behaviors have a bad effect on improving time management skills (Time Planning) (H4)	0.432**	Significant	There is sufficient evidence that Time waster behaviors have a bad effect on improving time management skills (Time Planning)	Approved
5- Good time management behavior skills (time planning) increase work quality and productivity (H5)	0.673**	Significant	There is sufficient evidence that good time management behavior skills have a positive effect on increase work quality and productivity.	Approved

However, the results of this study show that, in contrast, they are not productive. Therefore, companies must ensure discipline related to the work carried out by employees, even when working from home, so that tasks are completed in a timely manner. Supervision and communication are essential at the current time to ensure that employee productivity remains optimal. This form of management can be done by enforcing deadlines for each task and evaluating them periodically (Arop et al., 2020), This form of control can be done by enforcing deadlines for each task and evaluating them periodically (Arop et al., 2020). When regular monitoring and evaluation are carried out, it is hoped to become a new culture to remain productive (Filomachi and Stavros, 2017). Quick adaptation of all employees will ensure optimal productivity is maintained (Van Nguyen et al., 2021). In addition to supervision and control, companies should consider appropriate programs and incentives to increase productivity while demanding obligations from employees (Nwosu et al., 2020; Van Nguyen et al., 2021).

The findings of this study will certainly have an impact on company policies and strategies for increasing work

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

productivity. Allowing a combination of working from home and working from an office is expected to increase employee work productivity without reducing work-life balance and will keep employee stress at a manageable level. Face-to-face meetings are essential for developing new ideas and keeping employees motivated and focused, so having employees working from an office part-time is beneficial for companies. Companies also need to develop mechanisms and strategies to find positive methods to control the management of time and improve the skills used so as to make it a positive reflection on the work, comfort and efficiency of employees.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

In the current disruptive and very competitive world of work, managing time efficiently can be a key ability, not always innate but can be learned, which is why we consider it necessary that the university prepares students and embeds appropriate structures. The correct use of time is intimately related to the setting of short-term priorities and the attempt to fulfill them, for which it is not enough to rely only on memory alone, being also a necessary instrument to draw up lists of activities to be carried out. Instruments such as agendas (on paper, digital) play a very important role in this process. To get better time management the employees should use a diary to set goals and the technique of timeboxing to fix the time needed to finish each task, as this favors setting priorities and making decisions. When defending the dissertation or presenting any task/exercise required during working hours, the employees should also present the real-time box and explain the possible task differences. They must develop an awareness of where they spend their time and time tracking, learning to be flexible and to say “no” in order to avoid procrastination and distraction.

Research contributions and Recommendations

Research contributed to Highlighting the importance of the time management factor for companies and employees. Clarify different concepts to manage time in a simple and practical manner and understand the impact of good use of time management behaviors on the completion of the business and the mission. Clarify the difference between working from home and working from office and Careful field research to achieve real results that can be relied upon later. Knowing the best work environment suitable for employees to achieve efficient and high-quality work and Develop some scientific recommendations that consider its throat the beginning of many successful next steps.

The research has several implications starting with the implementation of training programs for students and fresh employees to learn about the importance of time management skills and how to develop these skills and the influential role of time management in practical life and Initiate the evaluation system using points based on measuring employees' behaviors and skills towards time management and its reflection on achieving goals and tasks within companies or even on those working from home. Expenditures should be increased toward entertainment methods to improve employee performance in the office so that the working atmosphere is pleasant and employees can perform successfully.

In order for employees who work from home to perform well, flexible work arrangements in the company should be made available and employers should supply ergonomic office items to improve the performance of employees who work from the office so that they could have to deal with any stress and pressure factors. Employees should supply ergonomic office items to improve the performance of employees who work from home so that they do not have to deal with any issues.

CONCLUSION

Finally, we can conclude that WFH and WFO have clearly been shown to provide major changes in organizational culture and work productivity in Egypt, Which means that the majority know well the importance of time management and its effect on their working lifestyle, They know that working from home is preferable for life health but it's not effective in accomplishing tasks and works needed to be done. These findings will certainly be the aim of further studies to explore deeper about the WFH concept and its impact on the broader organization. In addition to examining employees who work in the office.

It may be concluded that employees who work from the office have higher levels of productivity and performance than those who work from home. This result can be attributed to a number of factors. Some of the primary advantages that make the work-from-home concept beneficial for life health are reduced stress levels, connectivity with family, work convenience, and cost reduction.

LIMITATIONS

The sample size for this study is limited to the city of Cairo. It is recommended for future researchers expanded to include many different background career workers in other cities. A study on non-engineering background employees in other cities might also be undertaken to better assess the impact. Because the study is limited to employees of the engineering sector in a single city in Egypt, the findings may only be able to characterize the study's specific location rather than the entire universe. Employees that work from home and from the office provided data, and because they were preoccupied with their work, they were less responsive and preoccupied, however, there is a risk of biases in the responses, which is a major weakness of the current study. In-depth the study can be carried out on both WFH and WFO staff. By comparing the opinions of WFH and WFO, it is possible to gain a

Working from Home or Working from Office Understanding Time Management Importance and its Effect on the Job Outcomes in the Engineering Career Field

deeper understanding of the wide range of perceptions held by engineering personnel.

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